

Report on results - the relationship between the power and the temperature difference for four implants

Work package 4 - Uncertainty

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CONTENT

Scope	3
Abbreviations.....	3
The standardization background	4
Technical specification ISO/TS 10974	4
Technical report ISO/TR 21900.....	4
1. Definition of the task	5
Input data.....	5
The task	5
2. Solution.....	6
2.1 Definition of the solved task.....	6
2.2 Theoretical background	6
2.2.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$	6
2.2.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$	8
3. Transferring the deposited power into energy	9
3 Numerical results.....	10
3.1 Ankle Plate.....	10
3.1.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$	10
3.1.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$	10
3.2 Hip	11
3.2.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$	11
3.2.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$	12
3.3 Knee	13
3.3.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$	13
3.3.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$	14
3.4 Shoulder	15
3.4.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$	15
3.4.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$	16
3.5 All implants together.....	17
3.5.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$	17
3.5.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$	17
4 Summary.....	18
4.1 Summarizing the results	18
For the deposited power.....	18
For energy	18
Example	19
4.2 What we learned so far? Questions and answers.....	19
Annex A Graphical results.....	21
A.1 Ankle plate	21
A.1.1 Ankle plate - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$	21
A.1.2 Ankle plate - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$	23
A.2 Hip	25
A.2.1 Hip - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$	25
A.2.2 Hip - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$	27
A.3 Knee	28
A.3.1 Knee - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$	28
.....	30
A.3.2 Knee - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$	30

A.4 Shoulder	33
A.4.1 Shoulder - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$	33
A.4.2 Shoulder - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$	33
A.5 All four implants together	35
A.5.1 All four implants together - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$	35
A.5.2 All four implants together - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$	36

Scope

Determination of the relationship between the induced power and the temperature increase of the implant. Four implants are considered in this document:

- a. Hip
- b. Knee
- c. Shoulder
- d. Ankle Plate

Abbreviations

AIMD - Active Implantable Medical Device
 RF - Radiofrequency
 SAR – Specific Absorption Rate

THE STANDARDIZATION BACKGROUND

Technical specification ISO/TS 10974

Technical specification ISO/TS 10974 *Assessment of the safety of magnetic resonance imaging for patients with an active implantable medical device* in the point 8.4.4.4 *Procedure 3: Calibration of point temperature or SAR measurements to total dissipated RF power* states:

“The local temperature rise ΔT or SAR at a point location in a hot spot produced by the AIMD can be related to the total power deposition using a calibrated RF power injection method. The objective of this method is to calibrate ΔT or SAR measured at a specific spatial location to the total RF power dissipated at or near the AIMD hot spot. For each AIMD hot spot, a conversion factor m between ΔT or SAR at the hot spot and injected power is experimentally determined (i.e. $\Delta T = m \cdot P_{\text{inject}}$ or $\text{SAR} = m \cdot P_{\text{inject}}$) by injecting RF power..., and measuring ΔT or SAR at the hot spot for multiple values of P_{inject} .”

This means that a linear relation between ΔT or SAR at the hot spot and injected power is assumed. Finding such a relation is the main objective of this report on preliminary results.

Technical report ISO/TR 21900

Technical report ISO/TR 21900 *Guidance for uncertainty analysis regarding the application of ISO/TS 10974* in its part 4 introduces two methods for uncertainty evaluation (in practice, overlaps between those methods exist):

- a) Method 1 (part 4.2 of the TR) determines the uncertainty of the measurement system by considering the variability of the system as a whole. In this method, multiple elements of the system are assembled together, and their combined uncertainty is assessed. This is the method that we employed for evaluating the preliminary results, as presented in this report.
- b) Method 2 (part 4.3 of the TR) dissects the assembly into its parts, determines the uncertainty of individual elements, and then determines the uncertainty of the group by combining the uncertainty of the components.

The technical report ISO/TR 21900 in part 5 analyses the uncertainties present in the experiment for obtaining the relationship between the temperature increase of the implant, and the induced power (see ISO/TS 10974, part 8.3). It assumes that a measurement system consists of the RF field sources, tissue simulating phantom, probes for measurement of the temperature increase and for measurement of the induced power, and also a positioning system for the probes. All those parts contribute to the overall experiment uncertainty, and the technical report describes those contributions.

1. DEFINITION OF THE TASK

Input data

On January 18, 2023, the following files were received:

(Remark from INRIM) Each implant is associated with a activity1_.mat file containing the following variables:

- **power_map** : $N_\theta \times N_\phi$ matrix of the total power expressed in watts deposited into the implant for a specific orientation of the unitary harmonic magnetic field expressed in polar coordinates. θ : $[0, \pi/2]$ is the polar angle (the angle between the magnetic field vector and the z -axis), and ϕ : $[-\pi, \pi]$ is the azimuth angle (the angle between the magnetic field vector and the 1 x -axis). N_θ and N_ϕ are the numbers of θ and ϕ intervals at which the power has been computed;
- **power_worst_H** : 3-element vector representing the unitary magnetic field that results in the maximum power deposited into the implant;
- **temp_map_min** : $N_\theta \times N_\phi$ matrix of the maximum temperature increase expressed in kelvin, after minutes of exposure, for a specific orientation of the unitary harmonic magnetic field expressed in polar coordinates with the same criteria used in the **power_map** matrix;
- **temp_worst_H_min** : 3-element vector representing the unitary magnetic field that results in the maximum temperature increase after minutes of exposure;
- **external_surface** : external surface of the implant expressed in square meters (i.e., the interface between the implant and the background).

Each of the particular data files **power_map**, **temp_map_min** contains 40,000 data points (for any theta and phi combination it is one data point). The three files **temp_map_min** were received, for 5 minutes, 15 minutes, and 30 minutes.

The task

The text by INRIM, enclosed to data sets they sent, reads:

It is expected that the following points are investigated in the framework of the activity:

1. For each implant, the correlation between the magnetic field direction that maximises the power deposition into the implant and that maximises the temperature increase after 5 minutes, 15 minutes, and 30 minutes of exposure;
2. For each implant, the correlation between the power deposited into the implant and the following temperature increase as a function of the magnetic field direction. The correlation should be evaluated by accounting for a temperature increase after 5 minutes, 15 minutes, and 30 minutes of exposure;
3. For each implant, a coefficient, with associated uncertainty/confidence level, that allows estimating the temperature increase after a specified time instant given the power deposited into the implant.

2. SOLUTION

The following text of this document deals with point 3 of the formulated task, i.e. finding the dependence between the deposited power and a temperature rise, including the respective uncertainty.

2.1 Definition of the solved task

Therefore, the task is determining the relationship between the deposited power (denoted as X), and the temperature difference after a given time of 5, 15, and 30 minutes (denoted as Y). It is assumed that this relationship can be approximated by linear regression, i.e. a theoretical model is

$$Y = \beta X$$

or

$$Y = \alpha + \beta X$$

The task is to determine:

1. for $Y = \beta X$
 - a. estimate b the unknown coefficient β of the line,
 - b. the uncertainty u_b ;
2. for $Y = \alpha + \beta X$
 - a. estimates a and b the unknown coefficients α and β of the line,
 - b. their uncertainties u_a , u_b , and covariance among them u_{ab} .

If we determine those parameters, for any given x (the value of power) we can calculate the value of y (the temperature difference) and its corresponding uncertainty u_y . Moreover, an additional calculation was carried out, where the deposited power was transferred to energy, and the relation between energy and the temperature increase was investigated.

2.2 Theoretical background

The two forms of linear regression will be investigated:

- a. the linear regression (line) which crosses the zero point (intersection of x and y axes),
- b. the linear regression (line) which is shifted from the zero point (intersection of x and y axes)

2.2.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Employing the least squares method, the unknown coefficient b can be determined as follows:

$$b = \frac{1}{\sum x_i^2} \sum x_i y_i$$

where

x_i is the measured power input value (from the supplied data),

y_i is the measured temperature rise (from the supplied data).

2. The uncertainty u_b of the coefficient b can be determined as follows:

$$u_b = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum x_i^2}} s,$$

where s can be estimated by a formula for sample residual variance

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i - (bx_i)]^2}$$

3. The uncertainty u_y of the calculated value $y = bx$ can be determined as follows:

$$u_y = x u_b = x \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum x_i^2}} s$$

4. Coefficient of determination R^2 is a statistical measure of how well the regression predictions approximate the real data points

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - bx_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

5. Confidence intervals (UCL, LCL)

$$y \pm t_{n-1, 1-\alpha/2} u_y$$

$$y \pm t_{n-1, 1-\alpha/2} s \sqrt{\frac{x}{\sum x_i^2}}$$

6. Prediction intervals (UPL, LPL)

$$y \pm t_{n-1, 1-\alpha/2} s \sqrt{1 + \frac{x}{\sum x_i^2}}$$

7. Tolerance intervals (UTL, LTL)

$$y \pm k_{2, 1-\alpha/2, p, n} s$$

8. Uncertainty of conversion is determined as follows. The expanded uncertainty $U_{y, \text{conv}}$ of the temperature increase ΔT obtained by conversion from SAR is defined as half the interval between the upper and lower tolerance limits (UTL resp. LTL), the

interval that represents $(1-\alpha) \cdot 100 = 95\%$ certainty that there is a $p \cdot 100 = 90\%$ chance, that the correct prediction of ΔT lies between the upper and lower limits of the tolerance interval, i.e.

$$U_{y,\text{conv}} = k_{2,1-\alpha/2,p,n} S$$

where

$$k_{2,1-\alpha/2,p,n} = k_{2,0,975,0,9,n}$$

2.2.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Employing the least squares method, the unknown coefficients a , and b can be determined as follows:

$$a = \frac{\sum x_i^2 \sum y_i - \sum x_i \sum x_i y_i}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2}$$

$$b = \frac{n \sum x_i y_i - \sum x_i \sum y_i}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2}$$

2. The uncertainties u_a, u_b of both coefficients a , and b can be determined as follows:

$$u_a^2 = \frac{\sum x_i^2}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} S^2$$

$$u_b^2 = \frac{n}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} S^2$$

where

$$s^2 = \frac{1}{n-2} \sum (y_i - \hat{y})^2 = \frac{1}{n-2} \sum (y_i - a - bx_i)^2$$

3. The covariance $u_{a,b}$ between the two coefficients a , and b can be determined as follows:

$$u_{a,b} = \frac{-\sum x_i}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} S^2$$

4. The uncertainty u_y of the calculated value y can be determined as follows (the formula for u_y^2 is stated here):

$$u_y^2 = u_a^2 + x^2 \cdot u_b^2 + 2 \cdot x \cdot u_{a,b}$$

5. Coefficient of determination R^2 is a statistical measure of how well the regression predictions approximate the real data points

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - a - bx_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

6. Confidence intervals (UCL, LCL)

$$y \pm t_{n-1,1-\alpha/2} u_y$$

$$y \pm t_{n-1,1-\alpha/2} s \sqrt{\frac{1}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} (\sum x_i^2 + n x^2 - 2 x \sum x_i)}$$

7. Prediction intervals (UPL, LPL)

$$y \pm t_{n-1,1-\alpha/2} s \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} (\sum x_i^2 + n x^2 - 2 x \sum x_i)}$$

8. Tolerance intervals (UTL, LTL)

$$y \pm k_{2,1-\alpha/2,p,n} s$$

9. Uncertainty of conversion is determined as follows. The expanded uncertainty $U_{y,\text{conv}}$ of the temperature increase ΔT obtained by conversion from SAR is defined as half the interval between the upper and lower tolerance limits (UTL resp. LTL), the interval that represents $(1-\alpha) \cdot 100 = 95\%$ certainty that there is a $p \cdot 100 = 90\%$ chance, that the correct prediction of ΔT lies between the upper and lower limits of the tolerance interval, i.e.

$$U_{y,\text{conv}} = k_{2,1-\alpha/2,p,n} s$$

where

$$k_{2,1-\alpha/2,p,n} = k_{2,0,975,0,9,n}$$

3. Transferring the deposited power into energy

$$x/W = \frac{x/J}{t/s}$$

where

J is joule

W is watt

t is the respective time (5, 15, 30 minutes, converted to seconds)

3 NUMERICAL RESULTS

Based on theory stated in chapter 2, the following text contain calculated values for all four implants and for the two forms of the linear regression.

3.1 Ankle Plate

3.1.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{ankpla5m_b} =$	1,4712125 K/W	$u_{bankpla5m_b} =$	0,001575301 K/W
$R_{ankpla5m_b}^2 =$	0,87048183	$S_{ankpla5m_b} =$	$2,21147 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convankpla5m_b} =$	$3,63764 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{ankpla15m_b} =$	2,115517798 K/W	$u_{bankpla15m_b} =$	0,002179237 K/W
$R_{ankpla15m_b}^2 =$	0,881844433	$S_{ankpla15m_b} =$	$3,05929 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convankpla15m_b} =$	$5,03223 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

3. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{ankpla30m_b} =$	2,552769599 K/W	$u_{bankpla30m_b} =$	0,002517638 K/W
$R_{ankpla30m_b}^2 =$	0,892606045	$S_{ankpla30m_b} =$	$3,53435 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convnakpla30m_b} =$	$5,81366 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

4. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{ankpla_energy_b} =$	0.00167640 K/J	$u_{bankpla_energy_b} =$	$1.75226396 \cdot 10^{-6}$ K/J
$R_{ankpla_energy_b}^2 =$	0.70249781	$S_{ankpla_energy_b} =$	$5.00514001 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convankpla_energy_b} =$	$8.23295 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

Remark: Please note that the correlation coefficient indicates a weak linear relationship, compared to the dependence of temperature increase on the deposited power after 5, 15, and 30 minutes. Please compare with the correlation coefficient for $Y = \beta X$.

3.1.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n – number of points)

$(1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4)$

$a_{\text{ankpla5m_ab}} = 2.29836 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{aankpla5m_ab}} = 1.39716 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{ankpla5m_ab}} = 1.230235528 \text{ K/W}$	$u_{\text{bankpla5m_ab}} = 0.001990482 \text{ K/W}$
	$u_{\text{a,bankpla5m_ab}} = -2.04667 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{\text{ankpla5m_ab}}^2 = 0.90521686$	$S_{\text{ankpla5m_ab}} = 1.89187 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449 \quad U_{y,\text{convankpla5m_ab}} = 3,11193 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	

2. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n – number of points)

$(1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4)$

$a_{\text{ankpla15m_ab}} = 3.111633 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{aankpla15m_ab}} = 1.94668 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{ankpla15m_ab}} = 1.788778401 \text{ K/W}$	$u_{\text{bankpla15m_ab}} = 0.002773366 \text{ K/W}$
	$u_{\text{a,bankpla15m_ab}} = -3.97324 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{\text{ankpla15m_ab}}^2 = 0.912285715$	$S_{\text{ankpla15m_ab}} = 2.63597 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449 \quad U_{y,\text{convankpla15m_ab}} = 4,3359 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	

3. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n – number of points)

$(1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4)$

$a_{\text{ankpla30m_ab}} = 3.58566 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{aankpla30m_ab}} = 2.25212 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{ankpla30m_ab}} = 2.17682236 \text{ K/W}$	$u_{\text{bankpla30m_ab}} = 0.003208518 \text{ K/W}$
	$u_{\text{a,bankpla30m_ab}} = -5.3179 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{\text{ankpla30m_ab}}^2 = 0.920050979$	$S_{\text{ankpla30m_ab}} = 3.04956 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449 \quad U_{y,\text{convankpla30m_ab}} = 5,01622 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	

4. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n – number of points)

$(1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4)$

$a_{\text{ankpla_energy_ab}} = 5.41049901 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{aankpla_energy_ab}} = 1.57443568 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{ankpla_energy_ab}} = 0.00126533 \text{ K/J}$	$u_{\text{bankpla_energy_ab}} = 1.90940847 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K/J}$
	$u_{\text{a,bankpla_energy_ab}} = -1,88333940 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ K}^2/\text{J}$
$R_{\text{ankpla_energy_ab}}^2 = 0.78539134$	$S_{\text{ankpla_energy_ab}} = 4,25107123 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449 \quad U_{y,\text{convankpla_energy_ab}} = 6,99259 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	

3.2 Hip

3.2.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n – number of points)

$(1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4)$

$b_{\text{hip5m_b}} = 1.133156432 \text{ K/W}$	$u_{\text{bhip5m_b}} = 0,000464882 \text{ K/W}$
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$R_{hip5m_b^2} =$	0.774842384	$S_{hip5m_b} =$	$2.6571 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convhip5m_b} =$	$0.874 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{hip15m_b} =$	1.897958636 K/W	$u_{bhip15m_b} =$	0,000605093 K/W
$R_{hip15m_b^2} =$	0.782750617	$S_{hip15m_b} =$	$3.4585 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convhip15m_b} =$	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

3. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{hip30m_b} =$	2.49762561 K/W	$u_{bhip30m_b} =$	0.000734206 K/W
$R_{hip30m_b^2} =$	0.816735899	$S_{hip30m_b} =$	$4.19646 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convhip30m_b} =$	$1.38 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

4. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{hip_energy_b} =$	0.001580637 K/J	$u_{bhip_energy_b} =$	$1.11056 \cdot 10^{-6}$ K/J
$R_{hip_energy_b^2} =$	0.467604763	$S_{hip_energy_b} =$	$1.29154 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,645$	$U_{y,convhip_energy_b} =$	$2.12 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

Remark: Please note that the correlation coefficient indicates a weak linear relationship, compared to the dependence of temperature increase on the deposited power after 5, 15, and 30 minutes. Please compare with the correlation coefficient for $Y = \beta X$.

3.2.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{hip5m_ab} =$	$1.20576 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K	$u_{ahip5m_ab} =$	$8.38027 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{hip5m_ab} =$	1.09149561 K/W	$u_{bhip5m_ab} =$	0.002932398 K/W
		$u_{a,bhip5m_ab} =$	$-2.42651 \cdot 10^{-14}$ K ² /W
$R_{hip5m_ab^2} =$	0.775978489	$S_{hip5m_ab} =$	$2.65045 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convhip5m_ab} =$	$0,872 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{hip15m_ab} =$	$1.13769 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K	$u_{ahip15m_ab} =$	$9.38244 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{hip15m_ab} =$	1.504872446 K/W	$u_{bhip15m_ab} =$	0.003283074 K/W

	$U_{a,bhip15m_ab} =$	$-3.04156 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{hip15m_ab}^2 =$	0.840074435	$S_{hip15m_ab} =$ $2.96741 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convhip15m_ab} =$ $0,976 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$

3. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n – number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{hip30m_ab} =$	$1.3879 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$	$u_{ahip30m_ab} =$	$1.13623 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
$b_{hip30m_ab} =$	2.018085947 K/W	$u_{bhip30m_ab} =$	0.003975858 K/W
		$U_{a,bhip30m_ab} =$	$-4.46064 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{hip30m_ab}^2 =$	0.865616434	$S_{hip30m_ab} =$	$3.59359 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convhip30m_ab} =$	$0,59 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$

4. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n – number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{hip_energy_ab} =$	$2.59697 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$	$u_{ahip_energy_ab} =$	$2.76696 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ K}$
$b_{hip_energy_ab} =$	0.000930428 K/J	$u_{bhip_energy_ab} =$	$8.24191 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ K/J}$
		$U_{a,bhip_energy_ab} =$	$-1.91687 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ K}^2/\text{J}$
$R_{hip_energy_ab}^2 =$	0.913943425	$S_{hip_energy_ab} =$	$5.1926 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,645$	$U_{y,convhip_energy_ab} =$	$0,85 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$

3.3 Knee

3.3.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n – number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{knee5m_b} =$	$1,145453 \text{ K/W}$	$u_{bknee5m_b} =$	$0,000474923 \text{ K/W}$
$R_{knee5m_b}^2 =$	$0,95915549$	$S_{knee5m_b} =$	$2,95055 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convknee5m_b} =$	$4,85336 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$

2. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n – number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{knee15m_b} =$	$1,777887961 \text{ K/W}$	$u_{bknee15m_b} =$	$0,00063443 \text{ K/W}$
$R_{knee15m_b}^2 =$	$0,97002198$	$S_{knee15m_b} =$	$3,94152 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convknee15m_b} =$	$6,4834 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$

3. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n – number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{knee30m_b} =$	2.278559419 K/W	$u_{bknee30m_b} =$	0.000708149 K/W
$R_{knee30m_b}^2 =$	0.977212809	$S_{knee30m_b} =$	$4.39951 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convknee30m_b} =$	$7,23676 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

4. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J)
(n – number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{knee_energy_b} =$	0.00146018 K/J	$u_{bknee_energy_b} =$	$1.18299463 \cdot 10^{-6}$ K/J
$R_{knee_energy_b}^2 =$	0.68011614	$S_{knee_energy_b} =$	$1,49541816 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convknee_energy_b} =$	$2,45981 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

Remark: Please note that the correlation coefficient indicates a weak linear relationship, compared to the dependence of temperature increase on the deposited power after 5, 15, and 30 minutes. Please compare with the correlation coefficient for $Y = \beta X$.

3.3.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n – number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{knee5m_ab} =$	$3.3659 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K	$u_{aknee5m_ab} =$	$3.6362 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{knee5m_ab} =$	1.135547694 K/W	$u_{bknee5m_ab} =$	0.001170572 K/W
		$u_{a,bknee5m_ab} =$	$-3.89104 \cdot 10^{-15}$ K ² /W
$R_{knee5m_ab}^2 =$	0.9592295	$S_{knee5m_ab} =$	$2.94795 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convknee5m_ab} =$	$4,84908 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n – number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{knee15m_ab} =$	$-9.14039 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K	$u_{aknee15m_ab} =$	$4.86161 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{knee15m_ab} =$	1.780577858 K/W	$u_{bknee15m_ab} =$	0.001565058 K/W
		$u_{a,bknee15m_ab} =$	$-6.95554 \cdot 10^{-15}$ K ² /W
$R_{knee15m_ab}^2 =$	0.970024943	$S_{knee15m_ab} =$	$3.94142 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convknee15m_ab} =$	$6,48324 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

3. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n – number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{knee30m_ab} =$	$-3.22432 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K	$u_{aknee30m_ab} =$	$5.42472 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{knee30m_ab} =$	2.288048166 K/W	$u_{bknee30m_ab} =$	0.001746334 K/W
		$u_{a,bknee30m_ab} =$	$-8.66014 \cdot 10^{-15}$ K ² /W
$R_{knee30m_ab}^2 =$	0.977230186	$S_{knee30m_ab} =$	$4.39794 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convknee30m_ab} =$	$7,23418 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

4. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{knee_energy_ab}} =$	$1.97003520 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{knee_energy_ab}} =$	$5.25941303 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{knee_energy_ab}} =$	0.00104006 K/J	$u_{\text{bknee_energy_ab}} =$	$1.44127887 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K/J}$
		$u_{a,\text{bknee_energy_ab}} =$	$-5.89883549 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ K}^2/\text{J}$
$R_{\text{knee_energy_ab}}^2 =$	$0,81272095$	$S_{\text{knee_energy_ab}} =$	$1.14423361 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convknee_energy_ab}} =$	$1,88215 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$

3.4 Shoulder

3.4.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{should5m_b}} =$	2.28773545 K/W	$u_{\text{bshould5m_b}} =$	0.00040099 K/W
$R_{\text{should5m_b}}^2 =$	0.988382321011267	$S_{\text{should5m_b}} =$	$3.67294 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convshould5m_b}} =$	$6,04163 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$

2. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{should15m_b}} =$	3.56581087 K/W	$u_{\text{bshould15m_b}} =$	0.0005406969 K/W
$R_{\text{should15m_b}}^2 =$	0.99128182	$S_{\text{should15m_b}} =$	$4.95262 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convshould15m_b}} =$	$8,14656 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$

3. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{should30m_b}} =$	4.45101618 K/W	$u_{\text{bshould30m_b}} =$	0.00061052 K/W
$R_{\text{should30m_b}}^2 =$	0.99280986	$S_{\text{should30m_b}} =$	$5.592238 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convshould30m_b}} =$	$9,19867 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$

4. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{should_energy_b}} =$	0.00287617 K/J	$u_{\text{bshould_energy_b}} =$	$2.35930492 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K/J}$
$R_{\text{should_energy_b}}^2 =$	0.54590741	$S_{\text{should_energy_b}} =$	$4.39708632 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convshould_energy_b}} =$	$7,32772 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$

Remark: Please note that the correlation coefficient indicates a weak linear relationship, compared to the dependence of temperature increase on the deposited power after 5, 15, and 30 minutes. Please compare with the correlation coefficient for $Y = \beta X$.

3.4.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{should}5\text{m}_{ab}} = -7.38255777 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{should}5\text{m}_{ab}} = 4.92146463 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{should}5\text{m}_{ab}} = 2.44132357 \text{ K/W}$	$u_{b\text{should}5\text{m}_{ab}} = 0.00107459 \text{ K/W}$
	$u_{a,b\text{should}5\text{m}_{ab}} = -5.03894355 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{\text{should}5\text{m}_{ab}}^2 = 0.99231007$	$S_{\text{should}5\text{m}_{ab}} = 2.98831680 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449 \quad U_{y,\text{convshould}5\text{m}_{ab}} = 4,91548 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	

2. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{should}15\text{m}_{ab}} = -1.15296535 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{should}15\text{m}_{ab}} = 6.02977586 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{should}15\text{m}_{ab}} = 3.80567595 \text{ K/W}$	$u_{b\text{should}15\text{m}_{ab}} = 0.00131658 \text{ K/W}$
	$u_{a,b\text{should}15\text{m}_{ab}} = -7.56402739 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{\text{should}15\text{m}_{ab}}^2 = 0.99523567$	$S_{\text{should}15\text{m}_{ab}} = 3.66128416 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449 \quad U_{y,\text{convshould}15\text{m}_{ab}} = 6,02245 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	

3. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{should}30\text{m}_{ab}} = -1.36279491 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{should}30\text{m}_{ab}} = 6.53230859 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{should}30\text{m}_{ab}} = 4.73453459 \text{ K/W}$	$u_{b\text{should}30\text{m}_{ab}} = 0.00142631 \text{ K/W}$
	$u_{a,b\text{should}30\text{m}_{ab}} = -8,87736632 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{\text{should}30\text{m}_{ab}}^2 = 0.99638305$	$S_{\text{should}30\text{m}_{ab}} = 3,96642239 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449 \quad U_{y,\text{convshould}30\text{m}_{ab}} = 6,52437 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	

4. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{should_energy}_{ab}} = 6.83287867 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{should_energy}_{ab}} = 1.46611822 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{should_energy}_{ab}} = 0.00184608 \text{ K/J}$	$u_{b\text{should_energy}_{ab}} = 2.72507650 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K/J}$
	$u_{a,b\text{should_energy}_{ab}} = -3,24048231 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ K}^2/\text{J}$
$R_{\text{should_energy}_{ab}}^2 = 0,79272417$	$S_{\text{should_energy}_{ab}} = 2.97078161 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449 \quad U_{y,\text{convshould_energy}_{ab}} = 4,88664 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$	

3.5 All implants together

As a sample, evaluation for all data coming from all four implants at 30 minutes exposure were evaluated and the overall parameters were calculated.

3.5.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 16 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{all30m_b} =$	2,40313060 K/W	$u_{ball30m_b} =$	0,00067089 K/W
$R_{all30m_b^2} =$	0,97086364	$S_{all30m_b} =$	$5,69767662 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convall30m_b} =$	$9,37211 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power divided by the implant surface, exposure of 30 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 16 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{all30m_bS} =$	0,05714077 K/W·m ²	$u_{ball30m_bS} =$	0,00001001 K/W·m ²
$R_{all30m_bS^2} =$	0,98843460	$S_{all30m_bS} =$	$3,58971942 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convall30m_bS} =$	$5,90473 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

3.5.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n – number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 16 \cdot 10^4$)

$\alpha_{all30m_ab} =$	$4,45452985 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K	$u_{\alpha all30m_ab} =$	$1,90138367 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{all30m_ab} =$	2,25120807 K/W	$u_{ball30m_ab} =$	0,00089554 K/W
		$u_{\alpha,ball30m_ab} =$	$-1,23299078 \cdot 10^{-15}$ K ² /W
$R_{all30m_ab^2} =$	0,99231007	$S_{all30m_ab} =$	$2,98831680 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convall30m_ab} =$	$8,62823 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

4 SUMMARY

4.1 Summarizing the results

The following tables compare the results of the two approaches:

- with a linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$
- with a linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

The main idea is comparing the declination of the regression line, i.e. the parameter b , regardless the shift of the line (represented by a parameter a) is considered. To do so, the deposited power in W was transferred to energy in J . Four cases were compared - three related to the time (5, 15, and 30 minutes), and one for the whole set of 120000 points (for any combination of the angles θ and φ it is one data point).

For the deposited power

Table 4.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

	Parameter	5 minutes	15 minutes	30 minutes
Ankle Plate	$b_{ankpla_b} / K/W$	1,4712125	2,115517798	2,552769599
Hip	$b_{hip_b} / K/W$	1,133156432	1,897958636	2,49762561
Knee	$b_{knee_b} / K/W$	1,145453	1,777887961	2,278559419
Shoulder	$b_{should_b} / K/W$	2,28773545	3,56581087	4,45101618

Table 4.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

	Parameter	5 minutes	15 minutes	30 minutes
Ankle Plate	a_{ankpla_ab} / K	$2.29836 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$3.111633 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$3.58566 \cdot 10^{-11}$
	$b_{ankpla_ab} / K/W$	1.230235528	1.788778401	2.17682236
Hip	a_{hip_ab} / K	$1.20576 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$1.13769 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.3879 \cdot 10^{-9}$
	$b_{hip_ab} / K/W$	1.09149561	1.504872446	2.018085947
Knee	a_{knee_ab} / K	$3.3659 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$-9.14039 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$-3.22432 \cdot 10^{-11}$
	$b_{knee_ab} / K/W$	1.135547694	1.780577858	2.288048166
Shoulder	a_{should_ab} / K	$-7.38255777 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$-1.15296535 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$-1.36279491 \cdot 10^{-10}$
	$b_{should_ab} / K/W$	2.44132357	3.80567595	4.73453459

For energy

Table 4.3 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

	Parameter	Value
Ankle Plate	$b_{ankpla_energy_b} / K/J$	0.00167640
Hip	$b_{hip_energy_b} / K/J$	0.001580637
Knee	$b_{knee_energy_b} / K/J$	0.00146018
Shoulder	$b_{should_energy_b} / K/J$	0.00287617

Table 4.4 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

	Parameter	Value
Ankle Plate	$a_{ankpla_energy_ab} / K$	$5.41049901 \cdot 10^{-11}$
	$b_{ankpla_energy_ab} / K/J$	0.00126533
Hip	$a_{hip_energy_ab} / K$	$2.59697 \cdot 10^{-9}$
	$b_{hip_energy_ab} / K/J$	0.000930428
Knee	$a_{knee_energy_ab} / K$	$1.97003520 \cdot 10^{-9}$
	$b_{knee_energy_ab} / K/J$	0.00104006
Shoulder	$a_{should_energy_ab} / K$	$6.83287867 \cdot 10^{-10}$
	$b_{should_energy_ab} / K/J$	0.00184608

Example

As an example, the following table compares results for one case of exposure time and the same regression model. The last line represents the results for deposited energy divided by the surface.

Table 4.5 Comparison of parameters for 30 minutes exposure time and a model $Y = \beta X$

Implant	Model	$\Delta T \times 10^{-8} / K$	$U(\Delta T) \times 10^{-8} / K$	b	Deposited power $\times 10^{-9}$
Ankle plate	$\Delta T = b P$	0,003 - 0,06	0,006	2,55 K/W	0,01 - 0,09 W
Hip	$\Delta T = b P$	0,5 - 1	0,138	2,50 K/W	2 - 4 W
Knee	$\Delta T = b P$	0,06 - 1,1	0,072	2,28 K/W	0,5 - 5 W
Shoulder	$\Delta T = b P$	0,018 - 0,35	0,009	4,45 K/W	0 - 1 W
All 4 implants	$\Delta T = b P$	0,05- 1,1	0,094	2,40 K/W	$(0,5 - 5) \times 10^{-9}$ W
All 4 implants	$\Delta T = b \frac{P}{S}$	0,1- 1,1	0,0013	$0,057 K \frac{m^2}{W}$	$(1,1 - 19) \times 10^{-8} W/m^2$

It is worth noting from a physical point of view, one can observe a natural process of heating and heat transfer to the environment - the non-linear section of the graph indicates the heating of the implant itself from the moment the RF coil is turned on, and the linear section demonstrates the transfer of heat from the implant to the surrounding tissues.

With increasing time, the direction of the magnetic field for maximum temperature rise approaches the direction of maximum energy storage in the implant. At the time of 30 minutes, they are already close.

4.2 What we learned so far? Questions and answers

Following is a short summary of facts, what we learned so far by processing the obtained data, and what is still needed to do.

What we obtained in general?

The linear relationship between the deposited power (energy, power divided by surface) and the temperature rise.

Which form gets this relationship?	This relationship we can approximate by linear regression in the form $Y = b X$ (of a line crossing through the zero point) or $Y = a + b X$ (a line shifted from the zero point)
With which restrictions?	For each implant, we took all information on power and the respective temperature increase as data points, regardless of the combination of angles and also the time of exposure. In other words, we did not investigate the way data were obtained, and purely statistical methods were applied
What is the usefulness of obtained relationship?	We can select the maximum temperature increase and we can derive the deposited power related to that temperature increase
What we cannot say from the obtained relationship?	<p>We cannot say</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) the way the deposited power was brought to the implant. In other words, we know the relationship between the temperature increase and the magnitude of the incoming power, but we do not know the time of exposure and parameters of the magnetic field which generated the incoming power b) the influence of angles c) the influence of implant geometry with one exception, when we divided the incoming power by the surface of individual implants d) the maximum temperature at any given particular point of the implant. In other words, we know the general temperature rise in dependence on the acting power, either at one particular time or in a time interval, but not the temperature at any point of the implant e) the influence of time of exposure
What is needed in future investigations?	<p>For further use of the model and its better complexity, the following information needs to be obtained and implemented:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) A model relationship between the measured MRI machine input parameters and the generated power, acting on the implant b) Influence of implant geometry on thermal distribution c) Limits for permissible temperature increase, time limits, and other limitations for implant exposure (what is the longest exposure of the implant) d) Other

ANNEX A GRAPHICAL RESULTS

A.1 Ankle plate

A.1.1 Ankle plate - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

A.1.2 Ankle plate - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

A.2 Hip

A.2.1 Hip - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

A.2.2 Hip - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

A.3 Knee

A.3.1 Knee - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

A.3.2 Knee - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

A.4 Shoulder

A.4.1 Shoulder - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

Figures for individual times are missing

A.4.2 Shoulder - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

A.5 All four implants together

A.5.1 All four implants together - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

A.5.2 All four implants together - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

